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Global Ensemble Digital Terrain model and parametrization at 1 arc-second resolution

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Abstract—

This paper describes the first publicly available 1 arc-second global ensemble digital terrain model based on multi-source digital elevation models and its derivative parameters in multiscale (GEDTM30). A machine learning model was built from two global LiDAR datasets (GEDI02 and ICESat-2 ATL08) and two digital surface models (GLO30 and AW3D30). The model was trained by a global parent model using stratified global samples, followed by local child models to adapt diverse landforms. GEDTM30 reaches RMSE 2.74m in built-up area, 6.77m in forest, 3.36m in dense short vegetation. Furthermore, an automated pipeline was built to process the DTM into various land surface parameters, adopting the Equi7 tiling system, and implemented tile overlapping to mitigate border effects. Whitebox Workflows was used for parametrization and for hydrological correction on a large scale. The optimized pipeline allows the data to be updated within 48 hours.

I. INTRODUCTION

In geography, topography or relief are best represented by Digital Elevation Models [1,2]. DEMs are often used to measure the spatial variability in hydrological, geomorphological, and biological processes [3,4]. The need for a global DTM arises from the increasing demand for consistent and seamless terrain. Moreover, the wider user community, most likely requires a single best (ensemble) reference estimate of world elevations and is less interested in the complexity of ellipsoid, noise effects and artifacts. Besides, the facing challenge of land relief parametrization follows the higher resolution DTM product [5,6]. An optimized, scalable automation of parametrization is required to provide the wide user community of environmental research with an up-to-date ensemble DTM product and its parametrization.

This paper aims to bridge the gap of lacking a single consistent, open-source and complete estimation of world topography at 1 arc second and produces two main products: (1) the DTM product based on multi-source high quality world elevation data,

and (2) the automated global DTM parametrization process and products from the novel ensemble DTM.

II. RESULT

A. Production of ensemble DTM

We implemented a direct modeling of the terrain from DSMs to a DTM, fusing DSMs (GLO30 and AW3D30), vegetation object models, artificial object models, optical remote sensing indices and coarser DTM slope. In addition, we adopted a framework to train a “global-to-local” model in order to address the global diversity of land covers and landforms. “Global-to-local” modeling is a two-step transfer learning training framework: the global model with representative, globally stratified sampling, and the local model inherits the global samples with additional locally stratified sampling (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Visual explanation of the “global-to-local” transfer learning modeling. The system consists of M models where M corresponds to the number of tiles: M + 1 global model.

The “global-to-local” model preserves the generalization of the global model, but also reinforces the local features to achieve better performance. Figure 2 shows the visual comparison of the global versus “global-to-local” model. That additional local

training data improves prediction producing a lower difference between the reference model and GEDTM30.

Figure 2. Improvement of terrain modeling by a “global-to-local” model. Location shown: Trentino, Italy.

GEDTM30, is compared with the previous EDTM presented in Geomorphometry 2023 [7,8]. We aggregated the pixels from all the reference DTM sites [9] and group them by stable land use and land cover through GLAD Global LULC Change [10]. Table 1 summarizes RMSE, MAE and ME across the land cover. GEDTM30 performs better in all metrics (RMSE, MAE, and ME), notably, ME shows a drop to maximal 1m across in all land covers. These results suggest that GEDTM30 improves the accuracy in diverse land cover types from EDTM, making it a more reliable model for terrain mapping.

Table 1 Accuracy comparison between GEDTM30 and EDTM across different land cover types.

Dataset	Land cover (c)	Land cover (%)	RMSE	MAE	ME
EDTM	Cropland, stable	11.3	2.08	1.39	1.03
GEDTM30			1.54	0.93	0.38
EDTM	Built-up, stable built-up	12.5	3.78	2.27	0.57
GEDTM30			2.74	1.74	0.03
EDTM	Terra Firma, true desert	5.3	5.31	2.97	1.89
GEDTM30			2.65	1.55	-0.09

EDTM	Terra Firma, stable tree cover	15	9.9	7.01	2.07
GEDTM30			6.77	4.43	1.02
EDTM	Terra Firma, semi-arid	20.3	6.38	3.89	2.44
GEDTM30			3.41	1.98	0.65
EDTM	Terra Firma, dense short vegetation	15.9	5.65	3.44	2.27
GEDTM30			3.36	1.91	1.1

B. DTM parametrization Result

We implemented a pyramid-representative DTM parametrization to create multi-scale parameters at 30, 60, 120, 240, 480, 960m resolution. The multiscale process comprises two steps: (1) the DTM is down-scaled to coarse resolution, and (2) the original layer and the down-scaled DTM layers run the DTM parametrization independently (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Pyramid representation of DTM parametrization. Above: GEDTM30 at three scales; below: corresponding slope maps generated using WhiteboxTools.

To optimize the parametrization, a test was carried out by running the 60m resolution parametrization for all tiles. The processing time for each tile was recorded. Figure 5 illustrates the average individual and cumulative processing time of DTM parametrization in 60m resolution. According to Fig. 4, breaching depression takes the longest average processing time at 194 seconds per tile and the topographic wetness index takes the shortest to complete at the average processing time of 5 seconds. The complete computational workflow averages 742 seconds per 600 km by 600 km Equi7 tile at 60 m resolution. Extrapolating from this, a 30 m resolution parametrization is estimated to complete within a day, using 1,344 CPUs on 14 servers equipped with 1 TB of RAM each and connected to S3 storage servers with InfiniBand. Using this infrastructure, the possible update for the multi-resolution parameters can be completed in less than 48 hours.

Figure 4. Individual and cumulative processing times for DTM parametrization at 60 m resolution, averaged across all tiles.

A total of 15 land surface parameters (LSPs) from GEDTM30 are produced, including hillshade, slope in degree, negative openness, positive openness, profile curvature, minimal curvature, maximal curvature, tangential curvature, ring curvature, shape index, ls factor, difference from mean elevation, spherical standard deviation of normals, specific catchment area and topographic wetness index. Figure 5 is the example of all of the parameters in 1 arc sec resolution at Volcano National Park, the border of Rwanda, Uganda and Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC).

Figure 5. 15 land surface parameters derived from GEDTM30 in Volcano National Park, Uganda, Rwanda, and DRC

Figure 6 additionally illustrates the pyramid representation of the topographic wetness index (TWI) at different resolutions (30 m, 60 m, 120 m, 240 m, 480 m, and 960 m) in the Jhuoshuei River Basin, central Taiwan. The representation of the TWI pyramid in the alluvial plain highlights how the channel size and the distinctiveness of the cells evolve with increasing resolution. In the flat plain region shown in Fig. 6, the 30m resolution TWI clearly differentiates between wet and dry pixels. As the size of the grid increases, the primary channel becomes

more prominent and by the coarsest resolution (960m), the flat plain exhibits a nearly uniform wetness distribution. This multiscale TWI representation effectively captures a gradient spatial variability of wetness.

Figure 6. Mutli-scale topographic wetness index in Jhuoshuei River Basin at centre Taiwan

Ultimately, GEDTM and multi-scale LSPs results are produced in single files for each parameters in Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) and published under permissive license CC-BY 4.0 in Zenodo [11] and registered in OpenLandMap STAC (<https://stac.openlandmap.org>). Code and documentation to support reproducibility is distributed at GitHub (<https://github.com/openlandmap/GEDTM30>).

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